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Research Article

Use of the Internet as Source of Information for Students: A Case Study of University of Kotli AJ&K

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 18-Aug-23 Revised: 21-Sep-23 Accepted: 28-Sep-23 Published: 30-Sep-23	The major aim of the present study was to find out the use of internet as source of information by the students of University of Kotli AJ&K. The objectives of the study were to identify the use of internet as the source of information by students of University of Kotli AJ&K. The current study was descriptive by nature and survey method was applied for the collection of data. The population of the study was consisted of all 2994 students studying at BS level. Simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of sample. The researcher selected 341 Students as sample in this study. A five-point likert scale questionnaire was used as a tool in this study. The researcher personally visited the University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir and collected the data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage and mean for the analysis of data. It was found that students use internet for access online lecture and preparing presentation. It is recommended that to improve the habit of using the internet for entertainment purpose teacher may give awareness to the students to what extent they can use internet for entertainment.
Keywords:	Use of Internet, Source of Information, Electronic Mail, Social Networking, Entertainment
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Introduction

Internet is a helpful and effective method for students. Now the information age is the era in which we live where, in few clicks away we can get access to many internet resources. Internet is a technology like that, which has grown in acceptance everywhere. The internet serves as both a communication and informational channel. It makes it possible for researchers, businesspeople, information professionals, and students to access information to enhance their job and increase communication. The internet is a helping to connect each other. Some computers storing documents, such as web pages, that can accessible in all network computers. In the many websites that could be helpful to get information which he/she is needed (Strauss, 2003).

Fitzpatrick (2017) stated that Match.com, Reddit, Pandora, Wikileaks, Yahoo, Craigslist, Youtube, Facebook, Wikipedia, Amazon and Goggle are among the top 15 most influential websites ever named. There are many visitors of websites are tool for searching, and with the use of this tool, anyone can browse the internet with ease and find everything they're looking for. The information is not always correct. It is also replaceable and depending on when they require it (Robinson, 2006).

In our society libraries are fundamentally used in terms of social, cultural, and economic factors. They are stewards and collectors of our heritage; they gather and arrange our knowledge in the books, adding value by cataloguing, categorizing and describing them. They guarantee that all citizens have equal access because they are public institutions. They construct the foundation for the future using the knowledge of the past and present. (Reding 2005).

The core of the institution has traditionally been referred to as the library. It has been referred to as the academic community's brain. Eminent academics now assess a university's educational program based on how well its libraries are managed, such is the significance of libraries today. Despite this, it doesn't seem like the library's position within the academic establishment is the same at the moment. The advancement of technology, especially information and communication technologies, has resulted in a generation of students who view the Internet as the most recognizable, practical, and quick source of information today. These technologies include topic directories and search engines that are more comprehensive, relevant, and simple to use, such as (e.g., Yahoo and Google).

It is observed by the researcher that students of different universities have adapted and are still utilising the internet for their research and academic projects. Despite the abundance of information on the internet, relevancy, quality, and authenticity should not be overlooked. Students still use or prefer to use the internet as their information source. Hence, the researcher wants to conduct study on the use of the library and internet as sources of information by students of University of Kotli AJ&K.

Review of Related Literature

Internet

The internet is defined as the system of communication that links, connects, and transforms the entire world into a global village where people can easily get in touch with, see, or speak to one another and where people can instantly exchange information from one location to another (Shitta, 2002). People can use the internet as a practical information source for social, educational, and recreational reasons. The two primary uses of the internet are for communication and knowledge (Warren et. al., 2002).

Internet has many functions; it is important to know how much it can be used by the students in higher education for academic purposes. It is important to understand that the internet serves a variety of purposes, particularly in education as a repository of information, unlimited communication system, online interactive learning, online interactive learning, online research, it improves interest in teaching and learning process (Park, 2009).

Internet is considered an important aspect for getting education. A student or people who want to get information easily with low cost through internet. Any information may be found fast and readily on the internet, which is a vast reservoir of information. Students can access a range of instruction and knowledge via the internet. As in today, students dislike going to libraries or finding materials in the physical world, but they can access these locations online and can receive them quickly. The internet can be used as a tool to learn the most recent news from all around the world. Anyone can get information for hobby or health. Therefore, it can be spreader quickly beyond the confines of time and space, to a vast audience (Park and Biddix, 2008). It is important that to encourage the student to use internet to get valuable information. If the internet is not used effectively in education, its development would be pointless. Higher education institutions and other parts of the global educational system have been heavily impacted by new technology. Additionally, using the internet has the ability to raise educational standards (Charp, 2000).

Students can obtain knowledge on the internet, which also enables them to think critically and creatively. It equips students to work cooperatively and collaboratively to solve challenges (Dryli & Kinnaman, 2001). Students of today and aspiring knowledge professionals must obtain proper information. It is crucial for them to find the relevant information amid the innumerable informational tidbits. It is only one side of the core information to find the right information (Nentwich, 2003). It is very important to mention three important internet literacy as defined by Burgess (Burgess, 2006);

- i. Critical literacy: It is a comprehensive understanding of the internet that is socially contextualized.
- ii. Creative literacy: It is the ability to do experiment and abortion of information.
- iii. Network literacy: it is the ability to utilize internet-based tools for communication and knowledge sharing. (Burgess, 2006).

In the previous studies on internet we are examined that the majority of the students emphasized the variations in the learning outcomes. There is a difference between the courses taught by using internet and the courses which can be taught via traditional ways. It is a fact that students are not passive recipients of information when they access it online. It is important for the students to look the picture through their eyes to reach success (Benoit et. al., 2006).

Sources of information on Internet

The internet is becoming the vital component of our life. Most businesses today use the internet to run their operations. There are many uses of internet in which an individual and companies are making their daily task more comfortable and productive (Franz, Mallot, 2000). Here we are discussing the major uses of the internet which are playing an important role in our daily life.

Education

Education is playing an important role in fostering information and an understanding of sensations and emotions. It is also anxious with the change “how the people are acting after getting information and improving their lives and those of others” (Smith and Smith 2008). Many devices

nowadays are connected with internet. The internet has the capacity to provide comprehensive educational content on any subject in a variety of formats. People can learn about a range of topics by using the internet for just a few minutes. Search engines on the internet offer pertinent study material in a variety of media, including videos, photographs, documents, etc. It saves us time from having to visit the library and read a number of books to find the necessary knowledge. Additionally, Internet allows students to take online courses from anywhere in the world with the appropriate professors. (Larson, 2011). Social media apps and learning online platforms provide assistance teachers and students proper interaction whenever the need arises. A large number of online websites and data are able to provide real time updates. This allows the readers to provide up-to-date information, verified and ready for distribution (Franz, Mallot, 2000).

Research

It is a process used to gather and analyze data to better understand a particular topic (Creswell, & Garrett, 2008). In the field of research, the internet is essential. Finding information on any subject was quite difficult before the internet. People had to endure thousands of books for getting desired information. The information is an easy way of interaction for the researchers; because it helps as a source of direction and knowledge. It saves time of an individual. It is a useful tool for finding and has provided insightful academic study because it enhances research abilities and makes learning more visual and simpler to understand (Robin & Eisen, 2017).

Electronic Mail

People can swiftly obtain information and communicate data files, including music, video, image, and other forms of files, by using email. It also reduced the use of paper. Email is a simple way for everyone to communicate with others. It lessened the strain on the actual mail system as well (Gupta et al, 2000).

The user could send emails to friends, coworkers, etc. with the aid of the internet. Due to the incorporated application software, the internet might be seen as a strong publishing tool, with internet that allows an individual to communicate and transfer the information from one to another (Alemna, 2000). Nowadays students are using Electronic mail for many purposes like sending assignments to their teacher, sharing notes with colleagues, online discussion in groups for the purpose of learning. They use e-mail because It offers a written record, allows for the central storage and archiving of messages, and allows for the maintenance of the history of answers and forwards (Low, 2003).

Social Networking

A social networking site's (SNS) generative definition was presented by Boyd and Ellison in 2007: we define social network sites as services based on web which allows building public users can make a list of other users with whom they share link views, navigate their list of connections, and navigate the connections made by others using semi-public profiles and bounded systems. (Boyd and Ellison, 2007). Social networking is the largest platform to connect with others. People can share their knowledge through social media. It covers almost everything. It saves time and money. To use these services, people don't need to pay attention to anything. They can use these services free of cost (Oac, 2016).

Entertainment

Entertainment presents images of better things to escape into or things we desire but are sadly unable to have in our daily life. Hopes, wishes, these are utopian ideals; there is a sense that they could be realized (Dyer, 2002). Entertainment is the most effective means of internet. People can store movies, pictures, videos, song on local storage and can entertain when they feed easy. People can share their videos, songs, and photos with others by using the internet. People nowadays can watch live TV or programs on internet (Niels,2006). Play online games are another important source of entertainment on internet. There are many sites in which people can play online games freely. These games have made very popular among the young generation. Social networking has become a new craze for students. By chatting people can make new friends from one country to another (Garcia, 2010).

The role of Internet as sources of Information for Students

Internet helps the students to solve the problem. Students can benefit greatly from the internet. They may employ it for getting information. There are numerous websites that offer free lectures, and through marketing systems, students who live in remote places or are otherwise unable to access study materials can readily obtain them (Almahit, 2015). The internet is a useful resource for helping teachers and students with their research. Many colleges offer an online library system that enables students to access databases of scholars that they can read online or receive information about the books utilizing lab computers (Santos, 2003). The internet has permeated every home, business school, and government office in the world today and has become an essential component of daily life. Distances have been shortened thanks to the internet's communication infrastructure. The history of scientific inventions makes it clear that the internet cannot be compared to other historical inventions. It has created inconvenience in every walk of life especially in the field of research. There are definitely some advantages of internet. The library occupies a very important place in educational institutions. With its books, magazines newspapers, it appeals particularly to students who visit it to satiate their desire for reading resources that are unavailable to them in the classroom. The library has a highly positive impact on students' academic performance. (De Lasalle, 2019). Students can learn through the new technology. They can receive tutoring in schools and additional training online. In Philippine each student had their own methods for learning or acquiring extra knowledge for their academic goals (Espinosa, Laffey, Whittaker, & Sheng, 2006). The benefit of reading books that it is a one way to exercise the mind. It improves knowledge and keeps up-to-date. To ensure a better future for the next generation, the internet and literature should coexist. Students must maintain a healthy balance while studying. (Mapua ,2016).

The Internet is the most important resource that students use to attract the interest of numerous scholars. University students' use of the internet has been the subject of some study. For this reason, the research examined internet usage and general attitudes toward internet usage among students from the schools of science, arts, and business at the University of Dhaka in Bangladesh. So, the pupils each received a questionnaire and the data that had been gathered. As a result, the pupils returned 50 complete and valid questionnaires. The acquired data was then examined using SPSS. According to the findings, students majoring in business studies, science, and the arts use the

internet at rates of 100%, 92%, and 90%, respectively. According to the research, students with backgrounds in science and the arts should have more frequent access to the internet and spend more time using it. The research also suggests that institutions give all students access to internet services (Hossain & Rahman, 2017).

Objectives of The Study

1. To identify the use of Internet as the source of information by students of university of Kotli AJ&K.

Research Questions

1. To what extent education is source of information for students by using internet?
2. What is the role of internet as a source of information in terms of research knowledge?
3. To what extent internet as a source of information in facilitating electronic email for students?
4. What is the role of internet in providing social networking of students in the university?
5. To what extent internet provide academic entertainment to students in the university?

Research Methodology

The purpose of the study was to find out the use of Internet as the source of information by students of university of Kotli AJ&K therefore, the researcher used descriptive method of research in this study. In descriptive method the researcher used cross-sectional survey. Furthermore, questionnaire was used to collect data. All the BS level students currently studying in the University of Kotli were the population of Study. 2994 Students were studying at the BS level in the University of Kotli. The researcher selected 341 students as the sample of the study by convenient sampling technique. The sample was selected according to the Gay (2001) table. A questionnaire was formulated as a research instrument in this study. The questionnaire was based on the use of internet as sources of information. The parameters of internet were education, research, electronic mail, social networking and entertainment. Each parameter was consisted of 3 statements. Furthermore, Five Point Likert Scale was used for gathering the responses. Validity of instrument was checked by presenting the questionnaire to the experts of the field of education from University of Kotli AJ&K. The experts suggest changing in the questionnaire. They suggested that to omit and rewrite the statement no.3,7,9,8,15,18,23,24,27, and 30. The researcher incorporated changes in the questionnaire, as per suggestions. The researcher conducted pilot testing by distributing (30) questionnaires to those students. These students were not the part of final survey. The purpose of pilot testing was to check the adequacy, readability and reliability of the questionnaire. The reliability of instrument was measured through Cronbach's alpha statistic technique with the help of SPSS software. The reliability of the instrument was 0.80 which was acceptable for conducting the final survey. The researcher personally visited all the departments of University of Kotli and collected the data from BS level students. The collected data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The researcher applied frequency, percentage and mean scores for the analysis and interpretation of data.

Results

Table 1

Mean analysis of using internet for education purpose

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Using internet to access the online lectures	341	3.84
2.	Using internet for doing course assignments	341	3.58
3.	Using internet for preparing presentations	341	3.67

Table 1 illustrates the mean scores of reading books. The table further showed that mean score of using internet to access the online lectures; N=341, M=3.84, using internet for doing course assignments; N=341, M=3.58 and using internet for preparing presentations; N=341, M=3.67. Furthermore, the results indicated that the students used internet to access the online lectures has the highest mean score in using internet for education purpose.

Table 2

Mean analysis of using internet for research purpose

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Using internet for access of latest researches	341	3.40
2.	Using internet for analyzing the collected data of research	341	3.44
3.	Using internet for the collaboration with national and international authors	341	3.04

Table 2 illustrates the mean scores of research purpose. The table further showed that mean score of using internet for access of latest researches; N=341, M=3.40, using internet for analyzing the collected data of research; N=341, M=3.44 and using internet for the collaboration with national and international authors; N=341, M=3.04. Furthermore, the results indicated that half of the students used internet to access the online lectures has the highest mean score in using internet for education purpose.

Table 3

Mean analysis of using internet for E-mail

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Using Email for sending assignment to the teacher	341	3.45
2.	Using Email for sharing information with fellows	341	3.44
3.	Using Email for the purpose of chat	341	3.94

Table 3 illustrates the mean scores of research purpose. The table further showed that mean score of using Email for sending assignment to the teacher; N=345, M=3.40, using Email for sharing information with fellows; N=341, M=3.01 and using internet for the collaboration with national and international authors; N=341, M=3.04. Furthermore, the results indicated that half of the students used internet to access the online lectures has the highest mean score in using internet for education purpose.

Table 4
Mean analysis of using internet for Social Networking

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Using Social Networking for connecting academicians around the world	341	3.45
2.	Using Internet for social interaction	341	3.23
3.	Using Email for the purpose of chat	341	3.94

Table 4 illustrates the mean scores of research purpose. The table further showed that mean score of Using Social Networking for connecting academicians around the world; N=345, M=3.30, Using Internet for social interaction; N=341, M=3.23 and Using social networking for sharing study material to the fellows; N=341, M=3.29. Furthermore, the results indicated that half of the students used internet to access the online lectures has the highest mean score in using internet for education purpose.

Table 5
Mean analysis of using internet for Entertainment

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Using internet for watching interesting videos	341	3.25
2.	Using Internet for social interaction	341	3.23
3.	Using Email for the purpose of chat	341	3.94

Table 5 illustrates the mean scores of research purpose. The table further showed that mean score of Using internet for watching interesting videos; N=345, M=3.30, Using internet for playing games; N=341, M=3.04 and Using internet for watching movies online; N=341, M=2.97. Furthermore, the results indicated that half of the students used internet to access the online lectures has the highest mean score in using internet for education purpose.

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that students are using internet for educational purposes like; to access the online lectures, for doing course assignments, for preparing their presentations.
2. It is concluded that students using internet for the research purpose like; to access the latest researches, for analyzing the collected data of research. Furthermore, they are using internet for the collaboration with national and international authors.
3. It is concluded that students are using internet for electronic mail. Through electronic mail they are sending assignments to their teacher, sharing information to their fellows. But they are not using electronic mail for the purpose of chat.
4. It is concluded that students are using internet for connecting with social networking through which they are connecting academicians around the world, for social interaction. Furthermore, are they using social networking for sharing study material to their fellows.
5. It was concluded that students are using internet for entertainment purpose like; for watching interesting videos, playing games and watching movies online.

Discussion

Students are utilizing it to access online lectures, complete assignments, and prepare presentations. This trend aligns with the growing prominence of online learning platforms and digital resources in contemporary education (Barnes & Tynan, 2021). Students are tapping into its vast resources to access the latest research, analyze data, and collaborate with national and international authors. This reflects the global nature of academic research facilitated by digital connectivity (Bardzell & Bardzell, 2020). Email remains a crucial tool for academic communication among students. While it serves as a means to send assignments and share information with peers, the preference for academic tasks over casual chat underscores the professionalism associated with electronic mail in an educational context (Gray, 2019). The use of social networking platforms for connecting with academicians globally and fostering social interactions among students is on the rise. Such platforms also facilitate the exchange of study materials, further blurring the lines between formal and informal learning (Veletsianos, 2020). The internet's role in providing entertainment, from videos to gaming and movie streaming, continues to grow. This reflects the changing leisure habits of students in the digital age and the need for a balanced approach to internet use (LaRose et al., 2019).

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that university teacher may use multimedia projector in classroom and tell the students that how to use internet for educational purpose like; for doing assignments students need to discuss topic with someone, forums can be an excellent platform for students to discuss many topics, share knowledge and so on. It is recommended that teacher may encourage students to use and actively participate in forums of their assignment or presentation topic. So that students can easily prepare their assignments or presentations.
2. It is recommended that university teacher may guide students that for analyzing the collected data of your research use can use software from internet which is suitable for your research nature. It is also recommended that teacher may motivate students to collaborate with national and international authors by sharing their own new research ideas, while discussion with authors try to actively participate in the discussion.
3. It is recommended that university teachers may encourage students to use email for the purpose of chat because through email one can send a single message to a large group of fellows and also it provides a written record, messages can be centrally stored and archived and the history of replies or forwards can be maintained. It is recommended that teacher may tell these pros of email so they can use it for sharing information with fellows and for chatting.
4. It is recommended that university teacher may teach students how to be effective collaborators in that world, share your learning activities with the different academicians. It is also recommended that teacher may hold sessions on it.
5. It is recommended that teacher may give awareness to the students to what extent they can use internet for entertainment. Motivate students watch informative videos on internet, play games which lead them towards mental relaxation. So that students can use internet for entertainment purpose, play games and watching interesting videos.

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